

Methodology supplement **for the study on research ethics** **committee funding and prioritisation** **during COVID-19**

DOCUMENT INFORMATION

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Introduction

This supplement outlines the methodology used to develop the “Strengthening research ethics committees in crises: Why funding matters” and the “How-to guidelines for the prioritisation of research during global crises: a framework for research ethics committees”. The document provides details on the survey design, ethics approval, sampling, respondent characteristics, and analytic approach.

Study background

EUREC and the University of Vilnius conducted a survey in December 2024–January 2025 to identify research ethics committee (REC) challenges related to funding and the prioritisation of research during the COVID-19 pandemic. This survey addressed the following research questions:

- How, if at all, did resource availability impact the performance of RECs during the COVID-19 pandemic?
- What compensation models are currently in place for RECs globally, and how do they correlate with the perceived effectiveness of REC operations during the COVID-19 pandemic?
- How did RECs adjust their research prioritisation systems during the COVID-19 pandemic, including changes to criteria, structures, and processes?
- What were the operational and research-related consequences of these prioritisation changes?

The survey design was informed by the findings from the November 2022 survey conducted by PREPARED partner EUREC (Seedall & Tambornino, 2022) and insights from the PREPARED report "Recommendations for Expediting Ethics Review During Times of Crisis," which highlighted REC challenges experienced during the COVID-19 pandemic.

A comprehensive literature review was not conducted for this study. The literature consulted regarding the prioritisation of research was identified through consortium meetings, the PREPARED report on Recommendations for Expediting Ethics Review During Times of Crisis, and input from EUREC and PREPARED consortium members and advisors.

Target sample

Considering the varying operational structures of RECs — also known as institutional review boards (IRBs) and ethics review committees (ERCs) — across

different global contexts (e.g., Sambiéni, 2018; Hemminki, 2016), we targeted all staff members of RECs, including secretaries, chairs, coordinators, managers, and advisors, who served during the first wave of the COVID-19 pandemic (March–September 2020). To ensure clarity, participants were asked to base their responses on the role they held during the pandemic, rather than their current role, if it had since changed. One representative was contacted per REC to ensure that each REC was included only once in the study

Survey design and content

Respondents were asked about their primary role and responsibilities during the COVID-19 pandemic, the structure of their ethics review body and forms of compensation, the country location of their REC, the research topics their REC reviews, and their perceptions of the adequacy of compensation and preparation for the pandemic. Additionally, they were asked about the types of challenges they faced, their areas of greatest resource needs, relevant laws and regulations, systems for prioritising research during the pandemic, and the reasons for any changes made.

The survey incorporated a variety of question formats, including tick-box questions that permitted multiple responses, Likert-scale questions for ranking opinions and experiences, free-response queries, and multiple-choice questions.

Translation

The survey was translated into Spanish, French, German, and simplified Chinese using AI tools (DeepL, ChatGPT) to broaden its reach and accessibility across linguistic communities in Europe and globally. After the translations were completed, native speakers from the PREPARED consortium reviewed and refined them to ensure accuracy.

Pilot testing

A pilot of the survey was conducted in November 2024 with eight representatives from global RECs. The pilot was carried out to identify any issues with the survey's design, wording, or structure and to ensure that the questions were clear and appropriate for REC representatives. As only minor adjustments were made to the survey following the pilot, pilot responses were included in the subsequent analysis (see, e.g., Ruel et al., 2016, p. 117).

Ethics approval

The study underwent ethics review and was approved by the Joint Committee on Research Ethics at the Vilnius University Faculty of Philosophy (No. (1.13 E) 250000-KT-181). Informed consent was obtained through the completion and submission of the survey, as specified in the survey instructions.

Recruitment

The research team conducted an extensive search of RECs using the search engine Google. RECs were contacted based on the following search string in English, Spanish, French, German, and Chinese, depending on the local language of the country:

- "Research ethics committee [Country]" OR "Institutional review board [Country]" OR "Ethics review committee [Country]"

In addition, publicly available lists of registered RECs or REC networks were utilised for recruitment in relevant countries and regions.¹

A total of 1,973 RECs from 141 countries were contacted via email. Follow-up messages were sent approximately 3–4 weeks after the initial invitations.

In total, 324 responses were received, reflecting a response rate of 16.4%. Some RECs indicated turnover following the COVID-19 pandemic and high workloads as reasons for non-response. Additionally, language barriers may have contributed to the lower response rate.

While the use of publicly available online REC contact information enabled the research team to reach a diverse range of global RECs, it is important to acknowledge some limitations in the sample. Some REC contact information may not have been readily accessible in the study's languages, and certain RECs may not have an online presence or publicly available contact details.

Sample size calculation

Estimating the exact number of RECs worldwide is a complex task. The largest available registry of RECs is the US Office for Human Research Protections (OHRP) Database for Registered IORGs & IRBs, which lists 12,388 registered RECs

¹ These included member lists of EUREC (n.d.), the Forum for Ethics Review Committees in India – FERCI (n.d.) the SIDCER-FERCAP (n.d.) list of surveyors, the World Health Organisation List of National Ethics Committees (WHO, 2024), the Philippines list of Accredited RECs (PNHRS, n.d.), the list of accredited bioethics committees of Argentina (Government of Argentina, 2022), the List of Human RECs registered with NHREC (South Africa; 2021), Registered Health Research Ethics Committees in Nigeria (NHREC, 2011), among others.

as of March 2025 (HHS, n.d.). Using this figure as a proxy, with a 95% confidence level and a 5% margin of error, we needed approximately 370 responses to ensure a statistically significant sample size. While we received 324 responses, which results in a slightly higher margin of error, we believe that the broad geographic distribution, the diversity of REC characteristics, and our systematic recruitment approach make this sample reasonably representative.

However, there are limitations to this calculation: while many registered committees are global, the NIH is a US-based organisation, meaning the OHRP database may not fully represent the global REC landscape. Additionally, because the OHRP database does not provide contact information for registered RECs, we were unable to use it directly for recruitment purposes.

Respondent profiles

Respondents came from 80 countries: this represents around one-half of countries with any identified regulations for ethical review (see Tapscott & Machón, 2024). The continental distribution of respondents was as follows: Europe (38%), Asia (24%), North America (16%), Africa (7%), South America (8%), and Oceania (2%), with 6% of data missing. The highest number of responses were from the United States (10%), followed by India (9%), France (7%), Germany (4%), and the Netherlands (4%).

Due to the lack of comprehensive data on the global distribution of RECs, determining the representativeness of this sample is challenging. However, when compared to global population distributions and research ethics publication output, the sample appears to align with known patterns of overrepresentation in North America and Oceania, and underrepresentation in Asia and Africa (see Fig. 7 in Adjovi, 2025). Notably, our sample suggests an overrepresentation of European RECs.

Respondents were based in both high-income (52%) and low- and middle-income (42%) countries, when classified according to OECD (2022) data. This distribution may reflect the increasing presence of RECs in LMICs (Israel, 2015).

Respondents by country income level

Respondents by country

Respondents by continent

The respondents reported reviewing a diverse range of research types, with non-clinical health research (73.46%) and clinical research (70.99%) being the most prevalent. Other common areas included social sciences (50%), humanities (26.23%), and technologies (25.62%). Life sciences (25.31%), environmental research (13.27%), IT/engineering (11.11%), and physical sciences (8.33%) were also reviewed, though to a lesser extent. This distribution aligns with previous research indicating that approximately three-quarters of RECs review clinical and biomedical research (AAUP, 2000), while also reflecting the increasing regulation of social science (Israel, 2015), technology (Stahl, 2025), and humanities (Benčin et al., 2015) research.

Regarding the types of RECs, the majority were institutional (75%), followed by national (13%), regional (6%), and independent (4%), with only a small proportion being international (1%). Due to limited data on global REC distribution, as well as challenges identifying some subnational review processes at institutions (Tapscott & Machón, 2024), it is challenging to determine if these proportions are representative of the global REC population.

Quantitative analysis

Quantitative data were cleaned in Microsoft Excel and analysed using the software R. The data underwent manual correction to address inconsistencies. Additionally, data were transformed and prepared for statistical testing, including the creation of binary variables and categorisation of relevant factors.

The inferential analysis, performed in R, tested various independent variables, such as the selection of criteria like scientific robustness, order of submission, multiple responses, and feasibility, and their association with the perception of fairness, prioritisation, and challenges faced during the review process, among others. To explore these relationships, statistical tests, including t-tests, chi-square tests, and Spearman correlation, were performed to assess differences between groups and the strength of associations. Likert-scale data were treated as continuous in this analysis (for a summary of the current statistical debate, see Norman, 2010).

Qualitative analysis

The qualitative data, from the survey's open-ended questions, in Spanish, French, German, and Chinese were first translated into English via AI tools (ChatGPT). Then, these translations were checked by native speakers within the PREPARED consortium for accuracy.

The qualitative analysis of the survey's open questions was conducted separately from the quantitative analysis and was informed by the principles of inductive thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006).

For each question, the analysis followed these steps:

- (1) familiarisation with the data — understanding the question's purpose and context within the questionnaire, then reading all responses to gain an overall impression;
- (2) systematic coding of key ideas and meanings in the responses, from the first to the last (with multiple codes applied where relevant);
- (3) revising and refining codes — reviewing earlier responses in light of later codes, renaming, merging or deleting codes as necessary;
- (4) organising and describing codes in a structured format to support interpretation; (5) reviewing coded segments and restructuring codes where needed; and
- (6) developing and describing a narrative synthesis of the responses to each question.

Steps 1–3 were carried out in MAXQDA software, step 4 in MS Excel, and steps 5–6 in MS Word.

The analysis process combined an inductive, data-driven coding of responses with a subsequent interpretative phase informed by contextual knowledge of the research topic and survey design. This approach allowed for both an open exploration of participants' perspectives and a contextualised interpretation of the findings within the broader aims of the study. All analyses were discussed within the research team, and agreement on the final narrative structures was reached collaboratively.

For the two prioritisation questions, steps 5 and 6 were not applied, reflecting a pragmatic focus on capturing the most relevant insights within the available timeframe. Instead, selected findings from their qualitative analysis were incorporated directly into the development of the prioritisation guidelines.

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